

Experimental microbiological analysis of a UV-based sanitizing robot

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Abstract—In this work, a robotic solution for UV-based disinfection and its efficacy evaluation are presented. Experimental trials have been performed to compare the virucidal efficacy of common omnidirectional fluorescent UV lamps with respect to our solution which leverages a mobile manipulator equipped with a UV source as an end-effector. Such a source can be thus moved and oriented in order to reach those surfaces which could be potentially hidden by other objects during the sanitizing process. This is achieved through a surface-aware 3D coverage path planning.

Index Terms—Mobile manipulator, UV Disinfection, COVID-19, Coverage Path Planning, Microbiological analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The persistence of COVID-19 pandemic calls for the adoption of increasingly effective methods and solutions for sanitizing those areas shared by several people. A well-known disinfection technique consists in exposing surfaces to ultraviolet radiation (in particular the UV-C band) which causes the inactivation of pathogens, i.e. prevents their replication. However, accidental exposure of humans to UVC light can be harmful for eyes and skin. In this work, we present a robotic solution for UV-based disinfection and its efficacy evaluation compared against common solutions relying on omnidirectional fluorescent UV lamps. A microbiological analysis has been performed to assess the efficacy of both solutions during the experimental trials. The presented platform is the final prototype developed on top of the preliminary version described in our previous work [1].

II. RELATED WORK

Several solutions leveraging UV-based disinfection have been proposed in the literature to combat COVID-19 pandemic [2]. Environmental disinfection processes have usually been performed by means of omnidirectional fluorescent UV lamps, rigidly mounted on mobile platforms, moved either manually [3] or autonomously [4]. However, as underlined in [3], [5] the potential non-direct exposure to the UV source of some surfaces occluded by objects may limit or even nullify

This work is funded by Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca - FISR 2020 in the framework of the project "ARNOLD: AI-based full-coveRage AutoNOmous Local uv-Disinfection Robot" (proj. n.: FISR2020IP_02412) and by the University of Catania in the framework of the project Piano di incentivi per la ricerca di Ateneo 2020/2022 (Pia.ce.ri.) Linea 2D.

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the disinfection of such surfaces. This represents a main limit of those solutions adopting fixed emitting sources.

Other recent works relying on mobile manipulators are either teleoperated [3] or do not fully exploit the dexterity of the arm [5]. A very recent work proposes the combination of mobile manipulators and coverage planning [6]. The only assessment provided is in terms of estimated UV dosage rather than virucidal effect.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The final version of the prototype introduced in [1] is shown in Fig. 1. It consists in a differential drive mobile platform equipped with a 6 d.o.f. robotic arm, the Aubo i5. An RGBD camera mounted on the arm, the Microsoft Kinect, is used for the local point cloud reconstruction of the area to be sanitized. Such a point cloud is used to plan the 3D coverage path [1]. Moreover, the point clouds acquired by both the RGBD camera and an onboard 3D LIDAR, the Velodyne PUCK LITE, are used to build a local octomap which is used by the arm to plan collision free paths when performing the disinfection.

An Intel i9-based board is employed as computing unit and runs the Robot Operating System (ROS) software framework for the management of the arm, the sensors data acquisition, the 3D reconstructions and the activation of the irradiation sources. To carry out the experimental comparison, two different types of UVC sources have been installed on the platform: 1) a LED UVC source made up of four modules arranged to form a square, 2) a fluorescent UVC lamp installed at the rear part of the mobile platform. The remote-control station of the mobile robot is a laptop PC communicating with the platform via ROS, while an IP camera mounted on board of the vehicle continuously provides a visual feedback of the vehicle status.

The experimental trials aimed at providing a comparison of common disinfection processes obtained by translation of fluorescent lamps, with our proposed method which leverages: 1) surface-aware motion and orientation of the emitting source through the arm according to surface normals, 2) 3D coverage path planning as a sequential back-and-forth coverage on flat planar surfaces.

The main contribution of the present work compared to those in the literature lies in the microbiological experimental analysis of the virucidal efficacy compared to a fixed-direction emitting source.

IV. MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We tested the disinfectant property of the two types of UVC sources by placing a set of Petri dishes on a desk of an office-

Fig. 1. The prototype of mobile manipulator developed for the testing.

like scenario, as shown in Fig. 2. Two sets of dishes with different types of microorganisms have been used (namely *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Acinetobacter baumannii*).

The maximum distance of the scanning trajectory of the arm from the surface to sanitize has been set at 10 cm with an execution speed of 1 cm/s, thus obtaining an exposure time for a generic irradiated point of 16.5 seconds (taking into account the size of the LED square). On the other hand, the translation motion of the UV lamp is obtained from a linear motion at a cruising speed of 1.5 cm/s of the mobile base in front of the considered area. The source motion velocity for both the LED and the lamp have been computed taking into account the power of the source and the typical values reported in the literature for the inactivation of COVID-19 [4].

The results of these tests highlighted the virucidal capacity of the UVC LEDs on both types of microorganisms with a reduction of the bacterial load of 6-8 logarithms. The effectiveness of the omnidirectional UVC fluorescent lamp was comparable; however, a shadow area was observed in some Petri dishes partially occluded by objects on the desk, highlighted by the survival of the microorganism as shown in Fig. 3.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a mobile robotic manipulator with a UVC source for the disinfection of indoor environments. The experimental results confirm the actual impact of the usage of a mobile manipulator in order to ensure exposure to the UVC source to all those areas that could potentially be hidden. The results suggest that the combination of both the actions of the fixed lamp and the movable arm offers a complete and effective solution to sanitize the surfaces of an environment.

REFERENCES

[1] A. Borgese, G. Grassi, D. C. Guastella, G. Sutera, and G. Muscato, "Surface-aware ultra violet disinfection through a mobile manipulator," in *2021 I-RIM Conference*. I-RIM, 2021, pp. 5–7.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for the microbiological analysis with Petri dishes.

Fig. 3. Two Petri dishes with *Staphylococcus aureus* placed at the same position after the exposure to the two different UVC sources: in the one above an uncountable number of bacterial colonies survived, in the one below an abatement of 8 logarithms was observed.

[2] Y. Shen, D. Guo, F. Long, L. A. Mateos, H. Ding, Z. Xiu, R. B. Hellman, A. King, S. Chen, C. Zhang, and H. Tan, "Robots under COVID-19 pandemic: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 1590–1615, 2021.

[3] D. Conte, S. Leamy, and T. Furukawa, "Design and map-based tele-operation of a robot for disinfection of COVID-19 in complex indoor environments," in *2020 IEEE Int. Symp. on Safety, Security, and Rescue Robotics*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 276–282.

[4] L. Tiseni, D. Chiaradia, M. Gabardi, M. Solazzi, D. Leonardis, and A. Frisoli, "UV-C mobile robots with optimized path planning: Algorithm design and on-field measurements to improve surface disinfection against SARS-CoV-2," *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 59–70, 2021.

[5] A. G. Sanchez and W. D. Smart, "Towards verifiable COVID-19 aerosol disinfection using ultraviolet light with a mobile robot," in *The 14th Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments Conference*, 2021, pp. 300–305.

[6] I. Mehta, H.-Y. Hsueh, N. Kourtzanidis, M. Brylka, and S. Saeedi, "Far-uv disinfection with robotic mobile manipulator," in *2022 International Symposium on Medical Robotics (ISMR)*, 2022, pp. 1–8.